

THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING THE LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH)

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Abstract

Communities nowadays are dealing with a growing number of abrupt and significant changes as well as conflicts that impact social, political, and economic facets of daily life. In the millennial era, education's significance has also come under scrutiny. In actuality, curriculum design for 21st century learning needs to gradually change in order to emphasize the transferable skills that students must acquire in classroom environments. The kinds of abilities and competences that students must acquire in today's knowledge-based learning environment are different from those of the past. One of the most significant advancements in language teaching is the emphasis on communicative ability. Communicative activities in EFL/ESL classrooms prepare students to utilize English in other contexts, depending on their individual needs, interests, and opportunities.

Keywords: Communicative competence, communicative approach, social language, task-based language learning, text-based teaching.

Introduction

English's influence and function in the globe today are expanding at an accelerated rate. The primary causes of this phenomena are the increase in the speed and scope of information transmission in the global village as well as the expansion of communication with the globe following independence. English holds a strong dominant position in the online realm when it comes to the language of published content, which is a powerful incentive for individuals looking to advance their global competences to learn the language [1].

A communicative approach is an approach which is worldwide known and established it has established itself in many parts of the world as a way of teaching languages, especially English. It is the approach that has prevailed in English Language Teaching over the past 50 years, and it is still used nowadays [2]. The origins of the Communicative Approach are to be found in the late 1960s and early 1970s. The communicative approach is the product of some linguists and educators who had grown dissatisfied with the previous two methods used for foreign language teaching; the audio-lingual method and Grammar-translation method. These great linguists and educators who contributed to the rise of this worldwide used approach are Hymes, Chomsky, Wilkins, Van Ek and Alexander, and the Council of Europe. All of these linguists and educators believed, meanwhile, that pupils at that time were not picking up the language properly. They argued that actual language and the "whole language" were not taught to them. Pupils lacked the social language skills necessary to interact with people outside of the classroom in everyday settings. Thus far, they have depended on language structures rather than language functions and concepts. As a result, they were unable to interact with others in the language's culture [3].

Methods

The method of teaching second and foreign languages known as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) places a strong emphasis on interaction as the ultimate purpose of language

learning as well as its means. Another name for it is the "Communicative Approach." In the past, CLT has been viewed as both an expansion or improvement of the Notional-Functional Syllabus and a reaction to the Audio-Lingual Method (ALM). A more modern improvement on CLT called task-based language learning has seen a significant increase in popularity. A set of guidelines about the objectives of language instruction, how language acquisition occurs, the kinds of classroom exercises that promote learning, and the roles that teachers and students should play in the classroom can be referred to as communicative language teaching.

-Communicative competence includes the following aspects of language knowledge:

-Knowing how to use language for a range of different purposes and functions;

-Knowing how to vary our use of language according to the setting and the participants;

-Knowing how to produce and understand different types of texts;

-Knowing how to maintain communication despite having limitations in one's language knowledge.

So, Communicative Language Teaching is an approach to the teaching foreign languages that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language [4].

Principles of CLT:

-In the CLT approach, the meaning is given prime importance. The main focus of the approach is to make the learners able to understand the intention and expression of the writers and speakers.

-This method claims that language structures are not as significant as communicative functions. "Paying systematic attention to both functional and structural aspects of language, combine these into a more fully communicative view" is one of the most distinctive qualities of communicative language education, according to Littlewood. There are a finite number of sentence patterns in every language. Acquiring proficiency in solely those sentence structures does not help learners' ability to interact in the target language. The communication roles of those structures must be taught to the student.

-While using the CLT approach in teaching language, the target language is used in the classroom. The target language is a vehicle for classroom communication, not just the object of study [1]. Because if the learners continue to use their native languages, they are not able to communicate in the target language. It is believed that the native language should be used judiciously.

-The emphasis is on appropriate language use rather than accuracy. At a subsequent phase is accuracy. It's thought that correctness comes naturally to those who learn how to use the language correctly. Teaching language should involve the integration of various language skills, rather than focusing on just one. It implies that developing reading and writing skills is just as important as honing speaking abilities when it comes to communication strategies. It is impossible to learn a language by rote repetition. It is impossible to learn on its own. It ought to be acquired by social contact. One must struggle with language in order to communicate in the target language. According to Richards and Rodgers, the most effective way to learn the target language system is to struggle with communication. Making the student able to converse in the target language is the main goal when employing this method. The teacher accepts mistakes because the main goal is to help the students become proficient speakers of the target language. When students are engaging in tasks that require them to use the target language, the teacher shouldn't correct them. The instructor can point out the mistakes made by the students

and fix them. The CLT approach gives learners opportunities to communicate in the language of instruction. It promotes communication between students and between teachers. It facilitates the development of pupils' cooperative relationships. Work should be assigned by the teacher in groups or pairs so that students can exchange the material with one another. It facilitates their communication with one another as well. According to Richards and Rodgers, students are encouraged to engage with others through written work, pair and group projects, and in-person interactions. The CLT technique gives students the chance to practice saying things correctly as well as what to say. It is the teacher's responsibility to set up scenarios that facilitate communication. They should learn from the teacher how to utilize language in a social setting. The instructor must include exercises like role-playing that aid students in acquiring the language in a social setting. Techniques for teaching languages should be created in a way that motivates students to utilize the target language. Language's functional elements ought to be prioritized. To encourage genuine communication in the classroom, employ role plays, dramas, and games.

–It is important to provide students with opportunity to hear language in natural settings. They might receive coaching on techniques to increase their comprehension. [8]

As previously outlined, CLT can now be seen as describing a collection of fundamental assumptions about language learning and teaching, assumptions that may be used in various contexts and that touch on various facets of the teaching and learning processes. Some place a strong emphasis on the input into the process of learning. Thus, content-based education emphasizes that the entire process of learning a language is driven by the subject matter being taught. Certain teaching proposals place a greater emphasis on the processes of instruction. For instance, task-based training promotes using specifically created instructional tasks as the cornerstone of learning. Some emphasize learning outcomes and employ results or products as the foundation for lesson preparation, such as competency-based education and text-based teaching.

Conclusion

The communicative approach supports that learning is more student centered than teacher centered. A typical communicative language teaching lesson follows a PPP model. The teacher may present some part of the lesson, and students complete some exercises, but then students produce the language in freer activities that help them to communicate. As a result, the student talk is increased, whereas the teacher talk is decreased. The teacher establishes situations which promote communication and he facilitates students' communication. During the activities, he does not interrupt them, but he monitors their performance. Error correction is not immediate. If he notes a mistake and he realizes that he has to work on it, he does it later during a more accuracy-based activity. However, the role of students is to communicate by negotiating to mean. Even if their knowledge of the target language is not complete, they still have to try and make themselves understood, but also understand their classmates' intentions of communication.

The communicative approach is based on the idea that in order to learn a second language successfully, you have to communicate real meaning. Thus, when learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be active and used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language.

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